

Rethinking Online Community beyond Self-paced MOOCs

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Abstract. The rapid acceleration in the use of digital tools and platforms in education, driven by the COVID-19 pandemic, has also impacted Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), which are now available globally in various formats. An increasing number of individuals engage with these courses to enhance their knowledge, skills, and competencies for personal and professional development, benefiting from their free and easily accessible nature. This trend is also evident in our country, despite the absence of a definitive stance from European institutions regarding the accreditation and legal recognition of this type of education. Contemporary MOOCs increasingly emphasize brevity, conciseness, and reusability in their content design, prioritizing audiovisual materials over text-based resources.

This shift aligns with an increasingly fast-paced, flexible, and personalized approach to digital learning. Consequently, training providers face the challenge of ensuring the sustainability of these courses, as they must continuously produce and update materials that rapidly evolve.

In this context of fast, flexible, and at times consumer-driven self-directed learning, it becomes particularly relevant to reintroduce the value of socially oriented learning within MOOCs. This necessitates a critical examination of sustainable engagement and participation strategies.

This study, conducted by CREMIT (Research Center on Media Education, Innovation, and Technology) and ILAB (Center for Innovation and Development of University Teaching and Technology) at Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, aims to:

1. Compare the instructional models of pre-COVID (tutored) and post-COVID (self-paced) MOOCs, highlighting changes and challenges related to the social dimension of learning;
2. Identify signs of community formation within self-paced MOOCs;
3. Identify key conditions for fostering and sustaining a learning community that extends beyond the conventional MOOC lifecycle.

To achieve these objectives, the study collected and analyzed monitoring data from 33 MOOCs delivered between 2014 and January 2025. The dataset includes both quantitative data (initial and final questionnaires, learning analytics, and retention metrics) and qualitative data (analysis of forum messaging).

The contribution concludes with two forward-looking proposals: a hypothesis for the redesign of MOOCs, incorporating support tools for learner guidance and self-regulation; and the presentation of a new collaborative space dedicated to MOOC-

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related themes, envisioned as a platform for dialogue, reflection, and the co-design of new educational materials.

Keywords: Online Community, Community Development, Self-regulated learning.

1 Introduction

Since 2014, Cremit (Research Centre on Media Education, Innovation and Technology), in collaboration with Ilab (Innovation for Digital Didactics) of the Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, has been producing and delivering MOOCs as part of the University's Third Mission. These MOOCs focus specifically on prevention and digital media education to support a 'digital culture' [1].

The pedagogical model guiding these MOOCs is rooted in three key principles: the social dimension of learning, the knowledge-building approach [2, 3], and relational pedagogy [4]. These pillars drive MOOCs in a participatory direction, fostering communication and collaboration among participants [5].

However, the COVID-19 pandemic and subsequent lockdowns have significantly altered digital consumption patterns, both quantitatively and qualitatively. Education has seen a shift toward micro-learning (brevity and speed), ubiquitous learning (independent of spatial constraints, balancing synchronous and asynchronous elements), learner-centered approaches (catering to individual interests and needs), and the development of dynamic literacies [6]. This shift is also evident in MOOCs. When comparing pre-COVID and post-COVID MOOCs, we observe changes in time structures, an increase in self-paced learning, reduced feedback mechanisms, and fewer dedicated communication spaces. These adjustments, often responding to user requests rather than massive enrollment numbers, risk fostering self-learning processes with low participation density.

This shift necessitates an in-depth reflection on the pedagogical value of community, which remains a crucial element for learning. Designing MOOCs to encourage peer interaction, the sharing of best practices, and mutual support is essential [7]. This study explores sustainable engagement and participation strategies in self-paced MOOCs and examines how to extend the community beyond the course lifecycle. It does so through three key steps:

- comparing pre-COVID and post-COVID MOOC models, focusing on changes in social learning processes;
- identifying signs of community in post-COVID MOOCs;
- determining requirements for sustaining a learning community beyond a MOOC's cycle.

2 Impact of the "COVID-19" scenario on Cremit's MOOCs

From the inception of MOOCs at Università Cattolica, enhancing the social dimension has been a fundamental design principle [5], even within the light educational framework of MOOCs [8, 9]. The post-COVID redesign of MOOCs has aimed to support new forms of presence and participation. These dimensions have been systematically monitored through evaluation plans accompanying MOOC delivery since 2014. Monitoring includes participant feedback through final questionnaires, tracking data (a standard component of MOOC evaluation), forum message analysis, focus groups, and interviews conducted in various research projects.

In order to understand the changes in the social dimension, it is necessary to start by analysing the two MOOC models, with a few glances at the data.

2.1 The pre-COVID model

Between 2014 and 2021, Università Cattolica delivered 22 MOOCs via Blackboard's Open Education platform. These courses supported social learning through [5, 10, 11]:

- tutor facilitation and moderation;
- communication spaces (forums) for discussion and sharing;
- a communication plan designed to attract and engage learners actively;
- gradual content release to create an inclusive learning experience and mitigate dropouts typical of online courses. Table 1 summarises the design elements.

Table 1. Cremit – MOOCs Model from 2014 to 2021

Platform	Open Education by Blackboard
Orientation	FAQ
Materials	Videolessons + materials + e-tivity
Timing	Timed: weekly release (1 week socialisation + weekly module release + 1 week catch-up)
Duration	3 months
Tutoring	Asynchronous + synchronous
Communication	Alerts, e-mail, 6 threads in forum (Let's introduce ourselves, Reflections on the Honor Code, Doubts and difficulties with the platform, Let's discuss together, Questions on content, Assessment of the experience)
Assessment	Test at the end of each module
Certification	Certificate
Monitoring	Initial and final questionnaire

Tracking data indicates that this model was effective. Table 2 presents general tracking data on 20.987 enrolled participants. Of these, on average only 6.84% dropped out after the first week and 62.2% downloaded the course certificate, showing a very high completion rate compared to the 5-10% documented in the literature [12].

Tabella 2. Pre-Covid MOOCs

Learning Platform	No. Courses	No. Participants	No. Early drop-out (after 1 week)	No. Certificates	No. Final Q
Open Education	22	20.987	1.435 (6,84%)	13.048 (62, 2%)	9.637 (45,9%)

The second element is satisfaction: in the final questionnaires (N = 9.637), 49% of the users were completely satisfied, and 36.5% were very satisfied (using a 6-point scale, from 1=not at all satisfied to 6=completely).

A third element is related to student involvement. More than 95% viewed all the proposed content (with a functionalist-instrumental engagement) and 85% of forum messages were participant-generated, averaging 0.6 messages per participant (Table 6). About a quarter (24.91%) are 'communicative' participants in MOOCs. Furthermore, the final questionnaires show that:

- 12.2% identified as participative learners, 14% enthusiastic, 4.6% enterprising, 3.9% altruistic, 27% diligent, 1.3% lazy, 34% silent, 0.6% talkative, 0.5% pessimistic, 0.5% opportunistic, 0.6% dispersed/drop-out;
- tutoring scored 62% satisfaction and forum discussions scored 32% satisfaction;
- 31% felt involved in a learning community, with community members perceived as colleagues providing insights (27%), discussion partners (21%), sources of help (18%), professional contacts (32%), professionals in order to co-design resources and activities (27%).

Finally, the comparative analysis of messaging in the forums of 3 MOOCs, based on Gilly Salmon's *Five Step Model* [13], made it possible to observe a good qualitative level in the communicative exchange between e-tutors and students [14].

2.2 The post-COVID model

In the post-COVID period, from 2021 to the present, the design model of MOOCs has undergone several changes. One structural change was driven by the transition to a new platform introduced by the University, EduOpen, which conceptualizes communication spaces in a way that is more oriented toward courseware and less toward community engagement.

A second change concerns a shorter MOOC lifecycle, not only in terms of micro-MOOCs—characterized by a reduced overall duration, shorter modules, and more concise content—but also in terms of course sustainability, with fewer editions and less frequent content updates.

A third change has been driven by the economic sustainability of tutoring services, prompting a reconsideration of lighter forms of a role considered strategic [15], particularly in light of self-paced MOOCs. These MOOCs, in turn, challenge the existing model with the following demands: the ability to progress at one's own pace, necessitating the immediate and simultaneous availability of all materials; shorter course durations; a growing preference for synchronous over asynchronous

interactions, both among students and with tutors; reduced participation; and a tendency for students to produce and share content only when it contributes to workload assessment.

In this context, the post-COVID MOOC design (Table 3) seeks to preserve the social dimension of learning.

Table 3. Cremit – MOOCs Model from 2021 to 2025

Platform	EduOpen
Orientation	FAQ + minitutorial
Resources	Videolessons + materials + e-tivity
Timing	Open
Duration	10/12 months
Tutoring	Light tutoring Asynchronous
Communication	1 thread in forum
Assessment	End of module Test
Certification	Certificate
Monitoring	Final questionnaire

Since 2021, 11 MOOCs have been delivered, reaching 4.916 participants (Table 4).

Table 4. Cremit Light tutored+Self paced MOOCs 2021-2025*

Learning Platform	No. Courses	No. Participants	No. Certificates	No. Final Q
EduOpen	11	4.916	1.743 (35,5%)	2.919 (59,6%)

*Last updated date: January 14, 2025.

Final satisfaction surveys (N=2.919) reported a general satisfaction level of 52% (completely satisfied) and 30% (very satisfied). Additionally, 79% of participants engaged with all the MOOC content.

Despite the stability of the MOOC offering, participation patterns indicate significant shifts. Forum activity has notably declined, with an 81% share of messages generated by learners but at an average rate of only 0.1 message per participant.

Regarding discussion engagement, 47% of respondents rated forum discussions at level 6 on a satisfaction scale, while 44% reported feeling part of a learning community. This aligns with self-perceptions of participation: 14% identified as participatory, 17% as enthusiastic, 9% as proactive, 7% as altruistic, 21% as diligent, 1% as passive, 28% as silent, 2% as talkative, 1% as pessimistic, 1% as opportunistic, and 0.2% as disengaged/dropout. Participants perceived their peers in various ways:

- 34% saw them as colleagues who shared useful content;
- 33% viewed them as discussion partners on course topics;
- 30% considered them a resource for understanding complex concepts;
- 48% regarded them as potential professional contacts;
- 42% saw them as collaborators for co-developing activities, materials, and learning pathways.

In light of the relatively lukewarm participation data, this shift towards a lighter engagement approach appears to be the new lens through which learners interpret their participation, as reflected in the reported satisfaction levels. The social

dimension is not being eliminated; rather, it is still sought and enacted by participants, albeit at a different level.

3 Signs of community in self-paced MOOCs

To explore the persistence of community engagement in self-paced MOOCs, data collection focused on:

- Retention data: examining user loyalty and enrollment in multiple MOOCs.
- Final questionnaires: assessing satisfaction with learning community involvement.
- Forum exchanges: conducting qualitative analysis of discussions.

Retention Data. Table 5 presents the percentages of learners who, out of the total 4.916 enrolled in the 11 post-COVID MOOCs, chose to enroll in more than one of the courses offered. The data analysis suggests the presence of a critical mass of users interested in topics related to “digital culture”, who maintain their engagement and construct their own learning pathways independently, without these being explicitly proposed by the University. This group represents fertile ground for the emergence of a community driven by such participation.

Table 5. Retention

No. participants	Enrolled in 2 MOOCs	Enrolled in 3 MOOCs	Enrolled in 4 MOOCs	Enrolled in 5 MOOCs	Enrolled in 6 MOOCs	Enrolled in 7 MOOCs	Enrolled in 8 MOOCs
4.916	601 12,22%	119 2,42%	42 0,85%	21 0,42%	8 0,16%	5 0,10%	1 0,02%

Final questionnaires. The comparison between the answers to the final questionnaire of the pre-covid and post-covid MOOCs (Table 6) allows us to confirm the choices in the change of model, towards a dimension that accepts and welcomes lighter forms of participation in the training organisation. These results also tell of a pre-disposition of students to this dimension and not its “cancellation” for more self-instructive forms.

Table 6. Comparison of Pre-Covid and Post-Covid

	Pre-Covid	Post-Covid
Final questionnaire	9.637	2.919
Overall Satisfaction	49% completely satisfied 36,5% very satisfied	52% completely satisfied 30% very satisfied
Forum satisfaction	32%	47%
Involvement in community	31%	44%
Colleagues perceived as:		
· source of content	27%	34%
· possibility of comparison	21%	33%
· help in understanding contents	18%	30%
· professional contacts	32%	48%
· co-designer	27%	42%
Completion of activities	95%	79%
Forum		

· overall messages		
· n° messages participants	14.732	670
· n° messages tutor	12.491	541
Type of participant	1.792	129
· participative		
· enthusiastic	12,2%	14%
· enterprising	14%	17%
· altruistic	4,6%	9%
· diligent	3,9%	7%
· lazy	27%	21%
· silence	1,3%	1%
· chattering	34%	28%
· pessimistic	0,6%	2%
· opportunistic	0,5%	1%
· drop-out	0,6%	0,2%

Qualitative Analysis of Forums. The qualitative analysis of forums reveals participants' willingness to share a common interest within a perspective of learning and personal growth. These are signs of a community that emerges organically from participant interaction rather than being tutor-driven. This community engagement reflects an interest in course topics framed within a dynamic of exchange and relationship-building among peers. The types of contributions were classified as follows:

- Requests for discussion;
- Appreciation for course content;
- Personal reflections.

Similarly, the types of feedback observed included:

- Personal reworking of course topics;
- Sharing of resources;
- References to course materials.

Below are some qualitative examples of these messages:

Personal reflections: “[...] An increasingly common phenomenon is child influencers who, often pressured by their parents, are exposed on social media and lead highly stressful lives without the possibility of a normal childhood”. “There are laws and regulations, such as the Italian law on the protection of minors in television (e.g., the self-regulation code for television), aimed at shielding children from harmful content. However, the complexity of modern media makes it difficult to enforce these regulations consistently”. “What are your thoughts on digital media use for preschool children?” [*MOOC Infanzia Onlife: Gli adulti nell’educazione digitale*]

“This type of project should be strengthened to provide real employment opportunities for professionals in this field across the national territory, wherever interventions are needed to support the increasing fragility of the elderly, who are often overlooked”. [*MOOC Tutor di comunità*]

Requests for discussion: “I would like to ask what types of stories are most suitable for children—should they include rules, and can they address themes of loss?” [*MOOC Infanzia Onlife: Gli adulti nell’educazione digitale*]

“Being a caregiver is an act of love that is both deeply engaging and demanding. I feel that in terms of caregiver support, we are still far behind in meeting actual needs. Is this just my impression? Does anyone else share similar or completely different views?” [*MOOC Per una cultura delle cure palliative*].

Appreciation for course content: “This course is very interesting because it presents possible pathways and tools to be implemented locally, even in small communities.” “I appreciated the videos featuring real-life testimonies”. [*MOOC Tutor di comunità*].

Sharing of resources: “Books: *Il sentiero* by M. Dubuc; *Perché piangiamo?* by F. Pintadera and A. Sender; *L’anatra, la morte e il tulipano* by W. Erlbruch; *L’albero dei ricordi* by B. Teckentrup.” [*MOOC Infanzia Onlife: Gli adulti nell’educazione digitale*].

References to course materials: “I believe it is crucial to focus on Tisseron’s 3A approach—Accompaniment, Alternation, and Self-Regulation—so that digital proposals can be properly received and processed by children”. [*MOOC Infanzia Onlife: Gli adulti nell’educazione digitale*]

4 Community as a developed MOOC?

The analysis confirms the well-established importance of social interaction, even in MOOCs that are primarily designed for self-paced learning. We could suggest that the fifth step in Salmon’s model for online course development [13]—the development phase—represents the outcome of MOOCs, at least for some participants. This phase lays the foundation for the concept of a post-MOOC that nurtures an active community. If we consider that MOOCs can serve as the catalyst for activating communities that can fully leverage the social dimension [16], we must then examine the conditions that make the community the final stage in a MOOC’s life cycle. We identify three key conditions.

Identifying the target audience: Who should be engaged in the community-building process. Not all participants reach the fifth stage of Salmon’s model. Many drop out early, while others may only engage at the initial stages, where the experience is limited to information exchange (Salmon’s step 3).

Analyzing MOOC monitoring data allows us to identify participants who are most likely to thrive in a community setting—those who are open to building relationships, communicative, and deeply engaged with the topic. These ‘profile’ data help pinpoint the right audience for future proposals. Specifically, tracking participants who enroll in multiple MOOCs (retention) reveals a group with a deeper interest in digital topics, as well as a shared approach to understanding this phenomenon, including common themes, reflections, and language over time.

Through a targeted questionnaire administered to participants across at least three MOOCs, we aim to stimulate reflection on the community as a formative space for collective growth. The goal is to lay the groundwork for more direct involvement, turning the community into a purposeful entity that enhances the practices exchanged within it. Ultimately, this leads to the proposal of co-designing new MOOCs, ensuring

the university's engagement with stakeholders [17], and securing funding for their development.

Identifying the form of community: A community as a space for sharing and reflection, existing externally and post-MOOC, but preserving the memory of the course. The community becomes a way for course producers and providers to capitalize on the MOOC experience, making sense of its increasingly short but costly (both economically and educationally) lifecycle. Capitalizing means enhancing:

- Materials produced over time that are prone to obsolescence. Knowledge maps and the ways in which knowledge is mediated (such as the archaeology and history of knowledge) form a crucial archive for understanding the relevance of knowledge, maps, and methods—especially when knowledge pertains to the digital world. Making such content available in a community space serves as a memory of that community, creating an archive of work that allows future participants to align themselves with the community, foster reflexivity, and identify new training needs to address.
- Human capital of tutors and MOOC participants who have invested in the course. Their forms of participation will continue to benefit from the relational space within the community, where the return on their investment is seen in a more focused group than the original course participants.
- Forms of restitution. Exploring how the 'gratuitousness' of the MOOC can lead to generative processes on the part of the learner—asking, "What can I offer to others?"—within contexts that encourage and protect such sharing. This could sustainably generate collective benefits. However, this process is challenging in mass contexts where participation varies widely.

The proposal is to initiate a co-design phase for the community, involving some MOOC staff members and more active participants, as identified through monitoring. This will include a webinar for presenting the idea, two focus groups for comparing co-design phases (such as user involvement methods, community types, moderation styles, communication plans, monitoring strategies, and design repositories), and an evaluation of the sustainability of the proposed approach, which will be assessed through a questionnaire given to MOOC participants.

Supporting the value of the community: Enhance the attention to and value of the community dimension for all participants in Cremit MOOCs. While it's true that not all participants in a MOOC are ready for community engagement, this doesn't mean that the community aspect shouldn't be a focal point of reflection and support, especially with an eye toward future participation. Respecting each participant's individual learning path is essential, but MOOCs should be seen as spaces that reinforce this outward-facing dimension.

To this end, work is underway to redesign MOOCs to incorporate strategies that better support participants' self-regulation [18, 19]. Besides enhancing the formative aspect of the MOOC itself, self-regulation is crucial for participants to successfully engage in the social and community dimensions of the course. Therefore, the proposal is to:

- Include a module common to all MOOCs that addresses self-regulated learning, which is a critical aspect of online education. The module will begin with a

questionnaire to help participants assess their current learning habits and reflect on the various dimensions of regulation. Additional in-depth materials will be provided to support learners in effectively planning, monitoring, and evaluating their own learning progress.

- Revise the forums to optimize the tutor's role in promoting awareness of the significance of participation, using a 4-stage framework (Cluster, Orient, Focus, and Network) that has already been documented in the literature [20].

Each of these development proposals will be monitored to assess their impact on the community dimension, viewed as the outcome of a MOOC that doesn't end but rather regenerates throughout its lifecycle.

5 Conclusions

Community could ensure continuity to the social capital generated by MOOCs. To implement the project described in § 4, it will be necessary to revisit the community models proposed by literature to identify the one that best fits the identified needs, in order to initiate a pilot experiment.

This must be sustainable both for the organization activating the community and for the potential participating learners.

Regarding the moderation of the future community, it is necessary to better understand which actions to undertake to support it, also attempting to train AI-based interaction systems. In this regard, the categorization work carried out on the analysis of forum messaging (§ 3) will be useful. Shifting from a qualitative to a quantitative approach in communication analyses could also solve a limitation of the study.

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